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INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract:

Justice is considered as a major concern in our daily life, both in home or work related issues especially when decisions are made regarding limited resources. Human resource is considered as most powerful resource of a country to make it prosperous. All other resources like monetary resources, natural resources etc. are dependent on talented and capable human resources for their optimal utilization. Every employee wants justice in working environment, in terms of fair procedures used to determine rewards, distribution of rewards, interaction with supervisors to make them more satisfied and committed with their work and organization. Hence, the profession of doctors needs more attention, so they should be provided with such an environment where they will feel that they are being treated fairly well in every aspect and accordingly they will feel the need of disposing reciprocal response on their part to the organization in the form of Organization Citizenship Behaviours. The present study attempts to extend the existing empirical research on the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behaviour among doctors by investigating the relationship between the two variables among the doctors working in different hospitals in Srinagar, J&K state.

Key Words. *Organizational justice, Distributive justices, Procedural justices, Organizational citizenship behaviour,*

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary organizations throughout the world have realized that the vibrant business environment today is thronging unique set of opportunities & threats before the organizations. In order to survive & make maximum out of this dynamic business environment, the organizations and managers nowadays try to attract the best and the most professional human resource because of the well-known fact that employees or human resource is considered as one of the most valuable capital of organization, simply, the efficient and effective Human Resource is considered to be the backbone of the organization and the most important competitive advantage and the rarest source for the modern knowledge-based economy. This valuable capital that is Human Resource is the most important resource in comparison with others because of its tremendous influence on effectiveness of the organization. However, in effect to this, every employee is equally responsible for the growth of organization. So, in present era, the employee does not want a lot of monetary benefits and perks but recognition of work and also want justice in working environment,

in terms of fair procedures used to determine rewards, distribution of rewards, interaction with supervisors to make them more satisfied and committed with their work and organization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Justice is "the perception of individuals and group regarding fair treatment that they receive from the organization and their resultant reactions in behaviours to such perceptions" (James 1993). Justice researchers have identified three or four specific types of justice, each referring to fairness perceptions in a specific set of work contexts: distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice (sometimes broken down further into informational justice and interpersonal justice) (Byrne & Cropanzano, 2001).

Injustice and unfair distribution of achievements and output of the organization cause employees' demoralization and loss of their effort and activity morale. In fact, history is testimony to the fact that justice has been always expressed as an essential need for humans' social lives. Thus, justice is the secret of survival and sustainability of progress and development in organizations and their staff. Moreover, research literature has consistently shown that perceptions of organizational justice or injustice are a key factor affecting the attitudes and behaviors of individuals in organizations (Cole, Bernerth, Walter, & Holt, 2010).

In the first place, perceived justice affects attitudes towards work. Employees who perceive the workplace as fair are more satisfied with their work, are more committed to the organization, are more likely to rely on their superiors, and display a greater desire to retain their jobs (e.g., Loi, Yang, & Diefendorf, 2009). In contrast, employees who perceive injustice at work bring about negative attitudes toward their organizations, suffer from reduced personal welfare and achieve lower levels of daily functioning (Bobocel & Hafer, 2007). In jest, it can be concluded that if employees perceive that they are being treated fairly by their supervisors, they will be more likely to reciprocate by holding positive attitudes about their work, their work outcomes, and their supervisors (Wat & Shaffer, 2005). Specifically, research has consistently pointed to a positive association between perceptions of organizational justice and OCB, indicating higher OCB manifestations among employees who perceived that the organization and its leaders treated them fairly (while the converse relationship also held true). Moreover, Organ (1988) suggested that organizational citizenship behaviour might be "an input to one's equity ratio" and that employees respond to inequity by increasing or decreasing their levels of organizational citizenship behaviour.

Booming organizations have employees who go beyond their formal job responsibilities and freely give of their time and energy to succeed at the assigned job. Such behaviour is neither prescribed nor required; yet it contributes to the smooth functioning of the organization. In general, OCB refers to extraordinary efforts exerted by the employees beyond the demarcations of job description in the interest of an organization without reciprocity incentives. In the increasingly dynamic and competitive environment in which organizations operate, OCB is considered a highly valuable contribution to the effective functioning of an organization. Therefore, contemporary organizations need employees having organizational citizenship behaviour. Organizational justice has the potential to create powerful benefits for organizations and employees alike. These include greater trust and commitment, improved job performance, more helpful citizenship behaviors, improved customer satisfaction, and diminished conflict. Organ (1988) defines Organization Citizenship Behavior or simply OCB as the individual's behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization. Such behaviours are often described as behaviours that go beyond the call of duty and are often referred to as organizational citizenship behaviours. Organ (1988) identified five distinct dimensions of OCB: *Altruism* (helping specific others); *civic virtue* (keeping up with important matters within the organization); *conscientiousness* (compliance with norms); *courtesy* (consulting others before taking action); and *sportsmanship* (not complaining about trivial matters). And these dimensions have become widely accepted as they comprehensively represent the constructs on extra-role behaviour or voluntary behaviour proposed in previous studies (Yoon, 2009). Over the past three decades interest in OCB has increased substantially. There has been

numerous studies performed on organizational citizenship behavior and various antecedents of this behavior were explored.

However, there is no consistent conclusion on the relationship between organizational justice and performance, the proposal regarding the effect of organizational justice on performance regained respect when Greenberg (1987) introduced the concept of organizational justice with regard to how an employee judges the behaviour of the organization and the employee's resulting attitude and behaviour. Although, organizational justice has been investigated and found as a vital antecedent of OCB by many research studies. The present study attempts to extend the existing empirical research on the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behaviour among doctors by investigating the relationship between the two variables among the doctors working in different hospitals in Srinagar, J&K state.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is intended to focus broadly on investigating the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior among doctors in Srinagar. However, it focuses on the following specific objectives:

- To measure the level of organizational justice perceived by doctors of different hospitals of Srinagar City.
- To identify whether organizational citizenship behavior prevails among doctors of different hospitals of Srinagar city.
- To identify the relationship between organizational justice & organizational citizenship behavior among doctors in Srinagar.
- To provide suggestions to all doctors fraternity in general and in particular to the doctors of different hospitals of Srinagar city under study.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

For studying the relationship of organizational justice on organizational citizenship behavior, we test the following Hypothesis:

H1: There is a positive relationship between organizational justice & organizational citizenship behavior among the Doctors.

H2: There is a positive relationship between distributive justices on the organizational citizenship behavior among the Doctors.

H3: There is positive relationship between procedural justices on the organizational citizenship behavior among the Doctors.

Research Model for Present study

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The aim of present research design is to prepare a way of achieving the research objectives holding validity and reliability of the data. This study is a descriptive correlation study that seeks to explore the relationship between

organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior. The information for the study was gathered among doctors working in different hospitals of Srinagar city. The source of primary data is the response of doctors obtained through a questionnaire. Respondents are the Doctors who initially were reluctant to give responses; however, they were personalized promising anonymity. The primary data was collected from 5 Hospitals of Srinagar city. The hospitals included Shair-e Kashmir Institute of Medical Science (SKIMS) Soura, Government Medical Collage (GMC) Karanagar, Khyber hospital Khayyam, Kashmir Tibia Collage (KTC) Sadakadal & Lala Ded (LD) Lal Chowk. Sample was selected randomly with a view to analyze organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior among doctors. 105 questionnaires were distributed among respondents. Out of 105, only 82 questionnaires were received from the respondents, in which 10 were discarded because of inadequate information. Thus the total sample under study comprised 72 doctors from different hospitals of Srinagar city. Since the sample was drawn from the population of homogeneous group so the random sampling technique was adopted for the study. The responses were received from Doctors only to collect the information regarding various aspects of the present study. Data obtained was analyzed by using Software Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 16), Responses were recorded on a 5-point-Likert scale for OJ and OCB where 1 =Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree, and 5=Strongly Agree.

INSTRUMENT DEVELOPMENT

The Scale adopted for Independent variable (organizational justice) from Niehoff & Moorman (1993) and for dependent variable (organizational citizenship behavior) adopted from Podsakoff et al. (1990). Organizational Justice & Organizational Citizenship Behaviour Questionnaire containing 36 items that is assessed with its seven dimensions in which two belong to organizational justice (Distributive Justice (4 items) and Procedural Justice (5 items) and remaining 5 dimensions covering Organizational citizenship behavior consisted of 25 Items, Altruism, Conscientiousness, Sportsmanship, Courtesy and Civic virtue. In line with an empirical study of Karatepe et al. (2005), reliability test of the factors was carried out using Cronbach's alpha (α). Reliability of the factors refers to the accuracy with which the constructs repeatedly measure the same phenomenon within permissible variation (Table 1.1). An alpha score above 0.6 is generally regarded as an acceptable minimum level of sufficient accuracy for a construct (Hair et al., 2006)

DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS

After the data was collected, then it was carefully scrutinized and coded, so that the information could be brought to proximity. The data was analyzed by using following statistical tools.

- ✓ Correlation analysis was done using Pearson's Product Moment correlation to find out the relationship between the Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior.
- ✓ A simple linear Regression Analysis was done to find out the variance

DATE NORMALITY AND RELIABILITY

Table 1.1: SHOWING DATA NORMALITY

UNDER STUDY CONSTRUCTS	KURTOSIS	SKEWNESS	Reliability (α)
DISTRIDUTIVE JUSTICE	-.092	-.300	.856
PROCEDURAL JUSTICE	.183	.104	.773
ALTRUISM	-.089	-.453	.697
CONTIOUSNESS	.363	-.599	.816
SPORTSMANSHIP	.017	-.348	.745
COURTY	-.006	.392	.693
CIVICVIRTUE	-.440	-.615	.758

Tables 1.1 shows the normality of all variables & were found normally distributed. All skewness and kurtosis values were between -1 and 1. Hence observed result was found fit to carry subsequent analysis.

TABLE 1.2: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND CORRELATION MATRIX OF O J AND OCB.

VARIABLES	Mean	SD	DJ	PJ	AL	COI	SP	CO
DJ	2.99	.840	1					
PJ	3.00	.713	.439**	1				
AL	3.61	.690	0.76	.199	1			
COI	3.83	.559	.029	.281*	.562**	1		
SP	3.66	.516	-.197	.066	.277*	.683**	1	
CO	3.83	.471	-.081	.052	.408**	.293*	.312**	1
CI	3.53	.590	.288*	.432**	.356**	.337**	.073	.021

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

DJ:-DISTRIDUTIVE JUSTICE, **PJ;** - PROCEDURALJUSTICE **AL:-** Altruism, **COI:-** CONTIOUSNESS, **SP:-** SPORTSMANSHIP, **CO:-** COURTY, **CI:-**CIVICVIRTUE

Table1.2 shows that the Mean score of DJ and PJ items was found to be 2.99 and 3.00 on 5-likert scale which means that respondents were slightly agree with OJ and Mean score of OCB was found to be moderately (3.5 to 3.83) on 5-point Likert scale which means that respondents were moderately agree that they showing extraordinary efforts exerted by the doctors. The Results of correlation analysis between the variables are significant at p less than 0.01 and (DJ,PJ or OJ) are positively correlated to OCB dimensions. It is found that OJ has positive impact on OCB. It means that if employees find their organization just and fair in distribution processes, they are more inclined to show organizational citizenship behaviours which are helpful in progress of an organization. The results of this study support previous studies. Results proved that employees are more satisfied when they perceive their outcomes and rewards to be fair as compared to those employees who considered their rewards and outcomes as unfair. If employees feel discontent regarding their rewards they may decide to leave the organization (Y. Liu 2010). Relationship between organizational justice and OCB is also proved to be significant and positive, which implies that organizational justice resulted in demonstration of more OCBs from employees.

Table1.3 Showing results of Regression analysis between Predictors and Dependent Variables

Models	Relationship	Beta	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F value	T value	P value
Model I	Predictors: (Constant), OJ Dependent Variable: OCB	.201	.040	.027	2.950	15.88	.004
Model II	Predictors: (Constant), DJ Dependent Variable: OCB	.324	.104	.084	.4.401	21.41	.000
Model III	Predictors: (Constant), PJ Dependent Variable: OCB	.312	.097	.085	7.56	16.65	.000

Tables 1.3, Shows that the Regression between Independent variable (IV) OJ and dependent variable (DV) OCB the regression coefficient R is 0.201 which means that only 20.1% variation in the DV is due to IV and rest of the variance in overall OCB can be attributed to other factors which are held constant. Standardized β is 0.201 or 0.20.1% means that if there is one unit increase in IV then DV will increase by 0.20 units. F value is 2.95 and P value is also less than 5% so model is said to be fit. The results indicated that there is significant positive relationship ($r=0.201$, $P<0.05$) between organizational justice and OCB, consequently hypothesis 1 is supported (Model I).

The statistical analysis for (Model II) showed that the value of the calculated F was (4.401) and it is higher than the value of the tabulated F and the level of significance of (a) was (0.000) which asserted the rejection of the null hypothesis and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis which state that there is an impact of the distribution justice on the organizational citizenship behaviour of the Doctors. And the explanation of this result may reveal that the distribution justice in the Doctors is an element which is directly connected with the concept of the organizational citizenship behaviour. The results (Model III) showed that the calculated F value is (7.56) and it is higher than the tabulated F at the level of significance a (0.000). This means the rejection of the hypothesis and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis which states that there is an effect of the procedural justice on the organizational citizenship behaviour of the Doctors. And the explanation of this result may mean that the increase of the procedural justice in the Doctors enhances the organizational citizenship behaviour among the employees. And the researcher concluded from this that the Doctors of Srinagar city which work in the field of the procedural justice can raise the level of the organizational citizenship better than the Doctors that do not do so.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Employees are the backbone, the most valuable assets & living part of an organization that can make things happen, the practice of organizational justice is an inherent and inseparable part of the organizations' life. The attainment of organizational objectives largely depends on the motivation of employees to work and to their good perception of the organization. The condition of an organization's being effective or ineffective is mainly dependent on its human resource management in general and organizational justice in particular.

The result present study shows a positive relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior among doctors. It means that if employees find their organization justice and fair in distribution processes, they are more inclined to show organizational citizenship behaviors which are helpful in progress of an organization. The results also supported by Regression analysis showing positive relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior among doctors. As it can be shown from the hypotheses test results, there is a meaningful relationship between OJ with OCB. So, it is necessary to distribute and allocate resources and rewards justly in order to establish an organizational citizenship behavior in a way that staff can believe in justice observation. So it is better to make policies justly and to communicate with individual's carefully. The results of this study supported by previous studies. Results proved that employees are more satisfied when they perceive their outcomes and rewards to be fair as compared to those employees who considered their rewards and outcomes as unfair. If employees feel discontent regarding their rewards they may decide to leave the organization (Lee, 2000). However, relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behaviours is also proved to be significant and positive, which implies that organizational justice, resulted in demonstration of more organizational citizenship behaviours from employees organizational citizenship behaviours are important facilitators of organizational effectiveness. If managers and organizations want to foster them, they need to know how. Researchers have shown, both theoretical and empirically, that people adopt them when they feel fairly treated. Our research corroborates previous studies suggesting that employees display more OCB as more their perceptions of justice are positive. However, as the two-factor model predicts organizational citizenship behaviours in our study suggests that distributive justice and procedural justice explain organizational citizenship behaviours.

IMPLICATIONS FOR THEORY AND PRACTICE

The study represents the empirical research regarding the organizational justice and its consequences on work related outcomes (OCB) in health sector of Kashmir. Theoretically, this study adds empirical support to the assertion that organizational justice as one of the key indicators associated with employees 'willingness to go above and beyond their job requirements. The findings have implications for Human resource practitioners in showing the importance of organizational justice on employees' displaying of organizational citizenship behaviours. The study provides empirical evidence that in organizational contexts, efforts to increase organizational citizenship behaviours should be focused on treating employees with dignity, respect and stateliness especially through leader-subordinate relations. The present study on doctors of Srinagar city appreciate the need to treat valuable employees in a fair with

more emphasis on organizational justice so as to increase employees' sense of engaging in citizenship behaviours that benefits the organization as a whole.

This is in line with Weick's (1995) suggestion that employees serve as interpretative filters of relevant work events, features and processes. To this effect, organizational employees and supervisors must begin to view their functions and actions as messages and communications that have implications for modelling employees' fairness perception. Although organizational justice is an important factor in the effective functioning of the organizations (Greengberg, 2009), there is very limited research on this topic in Health sector of India especially in Kashmir. The present study provides the both theoretical and practical implications. This study revealed that how important justice perceptions of doctors are in determining their behaviours. OCBs are affected by justice in interpersonal working conditions, justice in procedures and justice in distribution of rewards. This study enhanced our understanding regarding the concepts of organizational justice, procedural justice, distributive justice and OCB. This study provides a basis for researchers in health sector for future research to further test the relationship of these constructs. The study provides authorities at top levels in the health sector with great insight into perceptions of Doctors regarding organizational justice and also provides with guidelines regarding how to enhance positive attitudes like OCB. Mean score of Organizational justice items regarding distribution and procedural justice was found to be 2.9 on 5-likert scale which means that respondents were slightly agree with organizational justice. It implies that attention should be given to improve the organizational justice practices so that doctors level of agreement on issues of organizational justice could move from slightly agree to strongly agree. Doctors of Kashmir were found to be slightly agreed to show OCBs. Policy makers should do efforts to improve the level of organizational justice sothat they show more OCBs which are crucial for successful organizations.

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